

Synthesis, characterization and biological activity of metal complexes with 4-aminoantipyrine Schiff bases of 5-chloro salicylaldehyde and 3-ethoxy salicylaldehyde

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Abstract : A series of transition metal complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV} with biological activity, have been synthesized involving the Schiff bases 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(5-chloro-2-hydroxy benzylideneamino)-pyrazol-5-one (5-Cl SALAAP), L₁ and 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(3-ethoxy-2-hydroxy benzylideneamino)-pyrazol-5-one (3-OEt SALAAP), L₂ derived from 4-amino antipyrine and 5-chloro salicylaldehyde/3-ethoxy salicylaldehyde respectively. Structural features were obtained from their IR, ¹H NMR, ESI Mass, UV-Vis, thermo gravimetric studies, elemental analysis, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements. Molecular modelling studies were also carried out to confirm the geometries of the complexes. The Schiff bases act as tridentate ligands which coordinate through the azomethine nitrogen, phenolic oxygen and carbonyl oxygen of antipyrine ring. The ligands and their metal complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli*. The results showed the metal complexes to be biologically active.

Keywords : Schiff base, amino antipyrine, metal complexes, antibacterial activity, molecular modeling.

Introduction

The Schiff bases and their complexes are widely studied owing to their increasing role in biological systems^{1,2}. These complexes are used, as catalysts, models for biomolecules and to emulate the activity of proteins³. The antipyrine derivatives are known to exhibit analgesic, anti-inflammatory⁴, antiviral⁵, antibacterial⁶, herbicidal⁷ and other activities⁸. Transition metal complexes with ligands derived from 4-aminoantipyrine also have significant biological activity⁹. Therefore it is worthwhile to synthesize a new series of heterocyclic Schiff bases containing the antipyrinyl moiety and their transition metal complexes.

The present paper reports the synthesis, characterization and antibacterial activity of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV} complexes of Schiff bases derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and 5-chloro salicylaldehyde/3-ethoxy salicylaldehyde.

Results and discussion

The Schiff base ligands 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(5-

chloro-2-hydroxy benzylideneamino)-pyrazol-5-one (5-Cl SALAAP), L₁ and 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(3-ethoxy-2-hydroxy benzylideneamino)-pyrazol-5-one (3-OEt SALAAP), L₂ are yellow coloured solids and are stable at room temperature. They are soluble in ethanol and dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO).

The complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV} with L₁ and L₂ ligands were found to be stable at room temperature and non-hygroscopic. They are insoluble in water, but soluble in DMSO and ethanol. All the complexes were characterized by various spectral and analytical methods. The proposed structures for all the complexes are presented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Based on the data of elemental analysis and ESI Mass, the composition was assigned to the complexes and presented in Table 1. The conductance values of all complexes were measured in DMSO solvent and also listed in Table 1. The results suggest the non-electrolytic nature of complexes in the solvent¹⁰ and also that no anions are present outside the coordination sphere.

Fig. 1. Proposed structures of (1 : 1) metal-ligand complexes.

Fig. 2. Proposed structures of (1 : 2) metal-ligand complexes.

Table 1. Physical properties and elemental analysis data of the ligands and their complexes

Compd.	Empirical formula	Mol. wt.	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Ω (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
						C	H	N	
5-Cl SALAAP (L_1)	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_2$	341	Yellow	161	98	63.18 (63.34)	4.45 (4.69)	11.6 (12.3)	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_1)\text{Cl}]$	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_3\text{CuO}_2$	439	Brownish red	197	75	49.27 (49.26)	3.41 (3.35)	9.56 (9.42)	19
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}_1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}]$	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_3\text{NiO}_4$	470	Brown	203	81	45.98 (45.45)	4.12 (4.09)	8.93 (8.87)	25.3
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_6\text{CuO}_4$	744	Brown	205	83	58.06 (57.98)	4.00 (4.04)	11.69 (11.29)	29
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_6\text{NiO}_4$	740	Brown	224	73	57.96 (58.30)	4.06 (4.05)	11.05 (11.35)	20
$[\text{Co}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_6\text{CoO}_4$	740	Green	237	92	58.73 (58.3)	4.06 (4.05)	11.05 (11.35)	22.2

Table-1 (contd.)

[Zn(L ₁) ₂]H ₂ O	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₆ ZnO ₄	745	Brown	221	88	57.9 (57.5)	4.26 (4.19)	11.26 (11.16)	13.2
[VO(L ₁) ₂ H ₂ O]	C ₃₆ H ₃₀ Cl ₂ N ₆ VO ₅	764	Brown	233	79	56.54 (55.51)	4.18 (4.23)	10.99 (11.21)	14.1
3-OEt SALAAP (L ₂)	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	351	Yellow	148	97	68.77 (68.57)	5.55 (5.98)	11.73 (11.95)	-
[Cu(L ₂)(H ₂ O) ₂ Cl]	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ ClN ₃ CuO ₅	485	Brownish red	208	86	49.48 (49.23)	4.94 (4.75)	8.65 (8.43)	28.6
[Cu(L ₂) ₂]H ₂ O	C ₄₀ H ₄₈ N ₆ CuO ₆	764	Brownish red	210	82	61.91 (61.87)	4.98 (4.83)	11.39 (11.23)	23.7
[Ni(L ₂)(H ₂ O) ₃ Cl]	C ₂₀ H ₂₆ ClN ₃ NiO ₆	498	Brown	211	79	48.20 (48.23)	5.22 (5.34)	8.43 (8.44)	24.2
[Co(L ₂)(H ₂ O)Cl]	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ClN ₃ CoO ₄	462	Brown	227	75	54.05 (54.09)	4.95 (4.94)	9.45 (9.33)	25.3
[Zn(L ₂) ₂]H ₂ O	C ₄₀ H ₄₀ N ₆ ZnO ₆	765	Brown	198	75	62.74 (61.87)	5.22 (5.32)	10.98 (10.87)	19
[VO(L ₂) ₂ H ₂ O]	C ₄₀ H ₄₀ N ₆ VO ₇	784	Brown	204	81	62.66 (62.78)	5.48 (5.67)	8.65 (8.43)	18

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectrum of ligand, L₁ is recorded in CDCl₃. ¹H NMR spectrum exhibits multiplet signals at δ 6.9–7.8 which are attributed to the aromatic protons, =C-CH₃ at δ 2.4, -N-CH₃ at δ 3.2, and azomethine proton (-CH=N-) at δ 9.8, intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH group at δ 13.5 as singlets¹¹. ¹H NMR spectrum of L₂ exhibits multiplet signals at δ 6.8–7.9, which are attributed to the aromatic protons. The methyl protons of the ethoxy substituent were observed as a triplet at δ 1.4, while its CH₂ protons appeared as a quartet at δ 4.1, =C-CH₃ at δ 2.4, -N-CH₃ at δ 3.2, and azomethine proton (-CH=N-) at δ 9.8, intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH group at δ 13.4 as singlets.

IR spectra :

The important IR spectral data of the ligands (L₁ and L₂) and their corresponding complexes are summarized in Table 2. The ν_{C=O} and ν_{C=N} (azomethine) observed at ~1648 cm⁻¹ and 1584 cm⁻¹ respectively in the spectra (except VO^{IV}-L₁) of the ligands show a downward or upward shift by 8–60 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes of L₁ and Cu-L₂ complexes. These are suggestive of the participation of the pyrazol-carbonyl and azomethine groups in coordination^{12–15}. In the spectra of VO^{IV} complex of L₁ and all other metal complexes of L₂, no shift is observed

in pyrazol-carbonyl (ν_{C=O}) band, indicating the non-participation of C=O group in coordination with the metal ion. The IR broad bands of metal complexes in the range of 3059–3553 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of coordinated/lattice water molecules as also supported by thermal analysis^{12,16–19}. The ν_{C-O} (phenolic) modes of the ligand appear in the region 1372–1383 cm⁻¹, shifted to higher frequency in the complexes indicate the complex formation via deprotonation of phenolic OH²⁰. The non ligand bands 523 to 587 cm⁻¹ and 434 to 459 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively²¹. In addition, the vanadyl complexes display a band at 968 to 980 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{V=O} modes²².

Electronic spectra and magnetic moments :

The electronic absorption (UV-Vis) spectra of metal complexes were recorded in DMSO, in the range of 200–1100 nm and the data is given in Table 3. The magnetic moment data and the proposed geometry of the complexes are also presented in the same table. These values are closer to those reported in some similar type of complexes.

The electronic spectra of ligand L₁ shows absorption bands at 41152 and 27548 cm⁻¹, while the L₂ at 33112 and 28818 cm⁻¹, which are due to the π→π* transitions²³. The electronic spectrum of 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-L₁ complex shows

Table 2. Infrared spectral absorption frequencies of ligands and their metal complexes (in cm^{-1})

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{OH}}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$	$\nu_{\text{V}=\text{O}}$
5-Cl SALAAP (L_1)	3448	1584	1648	1372	-	-	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_1)\text{Cl}]$	3443	1557	1635	1395	587	447	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}_1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}]$	3415	-	1632	1384	577	454	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3425	1515	1609	1383	548	465	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3415	-	1632	1386	577	437	-
$[\text{Co}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3411	-	1637	1386	575	474	-
$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_1)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3445	1565	1608	1389	572	470	-
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_1)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	3059	1592	1648	1373	562	445	968
3-OEt SALAAP (L_2)	3421	1586	1649	1383	-	-	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}]$	3382	1592	1658	1385	523	457	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_2)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3181	1581	1602	1386	553	431	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{Cl}]$	3061	1592	1650	1386	566	439	-
$[\text{Co}(\text{L}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$	3398	1593	1650	1385	566	443	-
$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_2)_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3553	1619	1649	1401	565	439	-
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_2)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	3407	1594	1651	1398	565	451	980

Table 3. Magnetic moments and electronic spectral data of complexes

Compd.	Absorption (in cm^{-1})	Transitions	Mag. moment (μ B.M.)	Geometry
5-Cl SALAAP (L_1)	41152 27548	$\pi-\pi^*$	- -	
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_1)\text{Cl}]$	41152 27548	INCT	1.71	Square planar
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}_1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}]$	19138 22222 17181 12500	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	2.67	Octahedral
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_1)_2]$	30303 23584 14285	INCT ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$	2.12	Distorted octahedral
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}_1)_2]$	23696 17271 12658	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	3.63	Octahedral
$[\text{Co}(\text{L}_1)_2]$	21645 16949 14285	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$	5.28	Octahedral
$[\text{Zn}(\text{L}_1)_2]$	-	-	Diamagnetic	Octahedral
$[\text{VO}(\text{L}_1)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	17857 25839	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$	1.73	Octahedral
3-OEt SALAAP (L_2)	33112 28818	$\pi-\pi^*$	-	-
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}]$	30668 21281 14148	INCT ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$	1.75	Distorted octahedral

Table-3 (contd.)

[Cu(L ₂) ₂]	37069 22.222 14005	INCT	2.05	Distorted octahedral
[Ni(L ₂)(H ₂ O) ₃ Cl]	23009 19920 17787	${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	2.31	Octahedral
[Co(L ₂)(H ₂ O)Cl]	37037 26954 19723	INCT	3.65	Square planar
[Zn(L ₂) ₂]	-	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ -	Diamagnetic	Square planar
[VO(L ₂) ₂ H ₂ O]	18867 25188	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$	1.94	Octahedral

INCT = Intra ligand charge transfer transitions.

broad band at 19138 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transition indicating square planar geometry²⁴. The observed magnetic moment (μ) value of same complex is 1.71 B.M., which supports square planar geometry.

The observed magnetic moment values of 1 : 2 Cu^{II} complex of L^I and 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 Cu^{II}-L₂ complexes (1.75–2.12 B.M.) fall within the range as observed for distorted octahedral geometry. Further the electronic spectra of these Cu^{II} complexes shows broad band in the range of 11376–19739 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, indicating distorted octahedral geometry²⁵.

The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes (of L₁ and L₂) show three absorption bands in the range of 9363–17800, 17000–19920 and 22222–23690 cm⁻¹, which can be attributed to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(v_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(v_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ transitions respectively and suggests octahedral geometry^{25,26}. The magnetic moment values of Ni^{II} complexes were found to be in the range of 2.31–3.63 B.M., which are in the range as observed for octahedral Ni^{II} complexes^{27,28}.

The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex of L₁ exhibits three bands at 14285, 16949, 21645 cm⁻¹, which can be assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively, suggesting an octahedral geometry around Co^{II} ion. The magnetic moment of the same complex (5.28 B.M.) also indicate octahedral geometry^{25,29}. The absorption bands in the electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex of L₂ at 37067, 26954 and 19723 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the

intra-ligand and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively, suggests square planar geometry³⁰ around Co^{II} ion. The magnetic moment (3.65 B.M.) also supports square planar geometry.

The observed magnetic moment value (zero) for Zn^{II} complexes indicate diamagnetic nature of the complexes. Based on analytical, conductance and spectral data, octahedral geometry³¹ for L₁ complex and square planar geometry for L₂ complex with Zn^{II} can be assigned.

The observed magnetic moment values for VO^{IV} complexes are in the range of 1.73–1.94 B.M., which suggests octahedral geometry for these complexes³². In the present study, all VO^{IV} complexes show two absorption bands, ~ 17900 and 25900 cm⁻¹, which corresponds to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions. These observations suggests, octahedral geometry for these complexes³³.

Mass spectra :

The Mass spectral data of ligands and their metal chelates are given in Table 4. Mass spectra of the ligands and their metal chelates show molecular ion peaks, which are in good agreement with the calculated values.

Thermal analysis :

Generally, two types of water molecules are associated with the complexes viz. lattice water and coordinated water. The lattice water will be lost at low temperature (60–120 °C) where as the coordinated water molecule lost at high temperatures (150–200 °C)³⁴. The representative thermograms of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of

Table 4. Mass spectral data of ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	Calculated mass	Obtained mass	Peak assigned
	(<i>m/z</i>)	(<i>m/z</i>)	
5-Cl SALAAP (<i>L</i> ₁)	341	342	M+1
[Cu(<i>L</i> ₁)Cl]	439	439	M
[Ni(<i>L</i> ₁)(H ₂ O) ₂ Cl]	470	470	M
[Cu(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	743.5	746	M+2
[Ni(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	738.7	740	M+1
[Co(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	738.8	740	M+1
[Zn(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	745	745	M
[VO(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂ H ₂ O]	764	746	M-H ₂ O
3-OEt SALAAP (<i>L</i> ₂)	351	353	M+2
[Cu(<i>L</i> ₂)(H ₂ O) ₂ Cl]	485	485	M
[Cu(<i>L</i> ₂) ₂]	763.5	764	M
[Ni(<i>L</i> ₂)(H ₂ O) ₃ Cl]	498.2	498	M
[Co(<i>L</i> ₂)(H ₂ O)Cl]	462.3	462	M
[Zn(<i>L</i> ₂) ₂]	765	765	M
[VO(<i>L</i> ₂) ₂ H ₂ O]	784	768	M-H ₂ O

both *L*₁ and *L*₂ indicate, (a) a small weight loss in the range of 60–120 °C which is assigned to the loss of lattice water, (b) maximum weight loss in the range of 150–200 °C attributable to the loss of coordinated water and (c) a gradual weight loss in the range of above 200–1000 °C can be assigned to complete decomposition of ligand moiety around the metal ion respectively. Finally the complex is converted to its metal oxide^{35,36}. The presence of

water molecules is further confirmed by the endothermic bands observed in the respective differential thermal analysis (DTA) curve in the temperature region, where the TGA curves indicate loss in weight. In addition to the endothermic bands, the DTA curves of complexes also show exothermic peaks, which are attributed to phase transition, accompanied by loss of water and decomposition of the complex.

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity of the ligands, namely *L*₁ and *L*₂ and their complexes with Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV} have been studied against *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by paper disc method. The concentration of these samples were maintained as 200, 100 and 50 µg/ml in DMSO. In the present study, the zones of inhibition of antibacterial activity have been presented in Table 5. The results indicate that the Co^{II} complexes show highest activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* at 100 µg and 50 µg/ml. The mode of action of the compounds may involve in formation of a hydrogen bond through the azomethine group with the active centres of cell constituents, resulting in an interference with the normal functioning of the cell³⁷. However, both the ligands were found to be biologically inactive.

Molecular modeling :

The possible geometries of metal complexes were

Table 5. Antibacterial activity and growth inhibition zone of microbes (in mm)

Compd.	200 µg/ml		100 µg/ml		50 µg/ml	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
5-Cl SALAAP (<i>L</i> ₁)	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Cu(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	7	7	-	-	-	-
[Ni(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	6	7	-	7	-	6
[Co(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	7	11	-	13	-	7
[Zn(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂]	5	7	8	-	7	8
[VO(<i>L</i> ₁) ₂ H ₂ O]	9	7	10	6	-	7
3-OEt SALAAP (<i>L</i> ₂)	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Cu(<i>L</i> ₂) ₂]	-	8	-	9	-	-
[Ni(<i>L</i> ₂)(H ₂ O) ₃ Cl]	-	9	-	-	-	-
[Co(<i>L</i> ₂)(H ₂ O)Cl]	8	13	12	14	-	15
[Zn(<i>L</i> ₂) ₂]	7	10	9	-	6	7
[VO(<i>L</i> ₂) ₂ H ₂ O]	8	6	10	7	9	-
DMSO control	-	-	-	-	-	-

evaluated using the molecular calculation with Arguslab³⁸ software. The geometrical optimization of the structures obtained are presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 3. Molecular modeling structure of Ni^{II}-L₁ (1 : 2) (227 kcal/mol).

Fig. 4. Molecular modeling structure of Co^{II}-L₂ (1 : 1) (567.2 kcal/mol).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. 4-Aminoantipyrine, metal(II) chlorides, 5-chloro salicylaldehyde and 3-ethoxy salicylaldehyde were obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Solvents such as ethanol, methanol, petroleum ether were purified by standard procedures.

Synthesis of ligands :

The two Schiff base ligands (L₁ and L₂) were prepared (Schemes 1 and 2) by mixing equimolar solutions of 4-aminoantipyrine with 5-chloro salicylaldehyde/3-ethoxy salicylaldehyde in ethanol and refluxing the reaction mixture for 2 h with constant stirring³⁹. The dark yellow solid product formed was filtered and washed with petroleum ether and recrystallized from ethanol. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC. Yield : 85-90%.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Synthesis of metal complexes :

In the preparation of the metal complexes, the metal ion salts and the ligands were mixed in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio using required quantities of ethanol. Hot ethanolic solution of ligand (0.01 mol) and hot ethanolic solution of corresponding metal salts (0.01/0.005 mol) MX₂ (where, M = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{IV}; X = Cl, for VO^{IV}, X = SO₄) were mixed together, refluxed for 2-3 h and left for evaporation at room temperature for 3 days⁴⁰. Coloured solid metal complexes were obtained. The products were filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried under vacuum over calcium chloride.

Spectral and analytical methods :

Elemental analysis of the ligands and their metal complexes was carried out using a Perkin-Elmer 240C (USA) elemental analyser. Molar conductances of the metal complexes were measured in DMSO solution using Digisun digital conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibilities of

the complexes were measured on Guoy balance, model 7550 using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard. The diamagnetic corrections of the complexes were done using Pascal's constants. TGA studies were carried on Shimadzu DTG-60 H system in the temperature range of 0–1000 °C. Melting points of the ligands and m.p./decomposition temperature of complexes were determined on Polmon instrument (MP-96). IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on Bruker FT-IR spectrometer from 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} . Electronic spectra were recorded with Elico SL 159 UV-Visible spectrophotometer from 200–1100 nm. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 , on Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer. The mass spectra were recorded by ESI technique on LCQ ion trap (thermo Finnigan Sanjose CA (USA)) mass spectrometer. Molecular mechanics calculations were done with Arguslab software, an interactive graphics program that allows rapid structure building, geometry optimization and molecular display. Molecular modelling software Arguslab has ability to handle transition metal complexes. Energy minimization was repeated several times to find global minimum.

Antibacterial study :

The antibacterial activity of the complexes was studied against Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*. The solutions of metal complexes and ligands were prepared by dissolving in DMSO at a concentration of 200, 100 and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Paper discs of Whatman filter paper no.1 were sterilized in an autoclave and saturated with solution of metal complexes in DMSO or DMSO as a negative control and were placed aseptically in the petridishes containing nutrient agar media inoculated with the above mentioned two bacteria separately. The petridishes were incubated at 37 °C and the inhibition zones were recorded after 24 h of incubation period.

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